

COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS : A THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Following recent works, it appears that the compressive strength in the direction of fibres of Glass-Epoxy and Carbon-Epoxy laminates depends on the loading and on the stacking sequence. It seems that the compressive strength is due to a microbuckling-type instability. In order to compute the critical load and the critical length of the phenomenon, an asymptotic study on a 2D laminate is done, and the influence of the structure on the critical stress and on the critical length is clearly shown. At the same time, complete calculations have been performed on the microstructure of the laminate and allow to confirm the results of the homogenized model.

Keywords : compression - strength - microbuckling - homogenization

1. INTRODUCTION

The compressive behavior of long-fibre composite materials and structures is somewhat difficult to characterize. Indeed, when comparing compression tests (pure compression or 4 points flexion) from different laboratories, a large degree of scatter is observed. The strain at failure of a T300/914 unidirectional is about 1,19% with a pure compression test [1], which is low as compared to the strain at failure in tension ($\approx 1,6\%$). But this strain reaches the value of 1,32% with a 4 points flexion test [2], and more than 2% with a "two knee-joints" buckling device [3].

It is first remarked that the strain at failure of Carbon-Epoxy laminates depends considerably on the mode of loading. This feature is also true when testing Glass-Epoxy laminates [4]. All these experimental results show the effect of the stacking sequence on the failure. More precisely, the influence of the plies at 90° and 45° on the failure strain and on the failure mode of T400/6376 laminates is shown on Figure 1, which is taken from the literature [3]. Vittecoq [2] obtained the same kind of results testing IM6/914 composites. His measured strain at failure is equal to 1% for a unidirectional specimen and 1,28% for a $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]_{6s}$.

To sum up, the mechanisms leading to the failure in compression are strongly dependent on the applied loading (compression or flexion) and on the stacking sequence.

Figure 1. Strains at failure of a T400/6376 UD, from [3].

2. EXPERIMENTS

In order to understand the longitudinal compressive behavior of long fibre composite materials, we have designed an experimental bending-compression set-up (see Grandidier and Potier-Ferry [4]). It allows to apply pure bending or mixed loading with various bending compression ratios. The device converts the uniaxial force of a conventional testing machine into appropriate efforts at the ends of the specimen. The different ratios of bending moment (M) to compressive load (N) are easily workable without complicated handling.

We have tested Glass-Epoxy and Carbon-Epoxy laminates (unidirectional plates and (0/90/0/90/Q)_s laminates). Concerning the compressive elastic behavior, the experimental results are the followings :

- The longitudinal elastic behavior of Glass-Epoxy composite is linear in the fibre direction,
- The behavior of Carbon-Epoxy is nonlinear.

This suggests that the nonlinear behavior of Carbon-Epoxy is mainly due to the fibre's behavior. As regards the strengths in the direction of fibres, it is shown that the strain at failure depends on the loading and is twice greater in bending than in compression.

3. MODELS

3.1. Background and review

Rosen [5] explained this phenomenon by a process of instability : the microbuckling of fibres. He schematized a unidirectional ply as a superimposition of hard and soft layers representing the fibres and the matrix. The critical stress is found to be equal to the global shear modulus of the composite in the plane of the fibres (denoted by G). For a T300/914, this leads to a microbuckling strain of the order of 3%, which is much higher than the experimental data [1] [2].

In order to improve the treatment of Rosen [5], many authors account for defects (fibre misalignment, plastic deformation in the matrix, fibre-matrix decohesion). For example, Argon [6], Budiansky [7], Budiansky and Fleck [8] search for the plastic instability (plastic kinking) in composites having an initial defect and a plastic matrix. They show that the critical stress is equal to :

$$\sigma_c = \frac{G}{1 + \frac{\Phi}{\gamma_y}} \quad (1)$$

where Φ is the initial misalignment angle and γ_y the yield strain in longitudinal shear of the matrix. Remark that this result gives the Rosen bifurcation stress for $\Phi = 0$.

In spite of the efficiency of this model, the main drawbacks are :

- we have no information about the wavelength of the phenomenon (kinking or microbuckling),
- these models are local and cannot account for the structural effect.

3.2. Homogenized model

An asymptotic study on a two-dimensional superimposition of hard and soft layers was proposed by Gardin and Potier-Ferry [9] (Figure 2). The macroscopic stress field is either linear (flexion) or constant (compression) in the transverse direction x_2 , and different boundary conditions can be applied on the upper and lower edges of the composite. This allows to couple the local and macroscopic effects.

Figure 2. Geometry without and with deformation

Linearizing the equilibrium equations around a state in small strain and uniaxial compression gives :

$$\frac{\partial S_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_\beta} - \Sigma \frac{\partial^2 u_\alpha}{\partial x_1^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{S} denotes the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, \mathbf{u} the displacement, and $\Sigma(\mathbf{x})$ the compression stress applied in the direction of fibres. We use an elastic and orthotropic constitutive law in plane stresses, and the continuity conditions for the displacement and for the stress vector at the fibre-matrix interfaces. Using the multiple scale method and taking into account the stiffness ratio as a small parameter, the following buckling equation is obtained :

$$-\frac{E_f h_f^2 f}{12} \frac{\partial^4 v(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1^4} + (G - \sigma) \frac{\partial^2 v(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_M^2} \frac{\partial^2 v(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $v(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the first approximation of the transverse displacement of the middle of the fibre, h_f the microscopic length defined on Figure 2 (width of the fibres), f the volume fraction of fibres, E_f the fibres Young's modulus, E_2 the global modulus in transverse tension, ν_M the Poisson's ratio of the matrix and σ the mean compression stress ($\sigma = f \Sigma_f$).

The first and second terms of equation (3) are similar to those obtained by Rosen. The third term of transverse derivative was already found by Grandidier and Potier-Ferry [4], and it permits to explain that the microbuckling depends on the stacking sequence and on the loading.

The main results of this homogenized model are :

- The displacement field in the fibre is a Love-Kirchhoff type.
- At first approximation, the stress in the matrix is a shear in the plane of fibres.
- The critical stress and the wavelength depend on the boundary conditions imposed through the laminate.

3.3. Consequences of the homogenized model

The homogenized model permits to find just as well the local modes as the global ones. Indeed, the homogenized potential energy is presented in the form :

$$P = 1/2 \int_{\Omega} f E_f \frac{h_f^2}{4} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x_2^2} \right]^2 + f E_f \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x_1} \right]^2 + (1-f) \left\{ G \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial x_1} \right]^2 + C E_2 \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial x_2} \right]^2 \right\} + \Sigma_f(x_2) \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial x_1} \right]^2 d\Omega$$

where $u(x_1, x_2)$ and $v(x_1, x_2)$ are the displacements respectively in the direction of fibres x_1 and in the transverse direction x_2 , and coefficient C is given by the homogenized model and depends on the volume fraction of fibres f and on the Poisson's ratio of the matrix ν_M .

If the displacement field is chosen in the form :

$$\begin{aligned} u(x_1, x_2) &= -y \frac{dV(x_1)}{dx_1} \\ v(x_1, x_2) &= V(x_1) \end{aligned}$$

it is possible to characterize the global buckling of the composite.

If now the displacement is chosen in the form :

$$\begin{aligned} u(x_1, x_2) &= 0 \\ v(x_1, x_2) &= f(x_2) \sin kx_1 \end{aligned}$$

The critical stress of local buckling is equal to :

$$\sigma_c = G + \frac{\pi h_f}{2 H} \sqrt{f} \sqrt{E_f E_2} \quad (4)$$

And the wavelength is :

$$l_c = 2 \sqrt{\pi} \sqrt[4]{\frac{E_f}{C E_2}} \sqrt{\frac{H h_f}{2 \sqrt{3}}} \quad (5)$$

where H is a characteristic length which depends on the boundary conditions imposed through the laminate.

3.4. Calculation of the complete microstructure

In order to validate the results given by the homogenized model, we have computed the critical load and the critical length on the complete microstructure of the composite. As it was not possible to do a parametric study using classical finite elements, we developed a unidimensional element specific to our

problem. The laminate is completely described, that is to say that the plies at 0° are represented by a superimposition of hard and soft layers (fibres, matrix), and the plies at 90° or 45° by layers having the same thickness and the same mechanical characteristics (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Description of the microstructure

Two types of loading are applied : a constant strain in the thickness and a linear strain. The materials constituting the laminate are supposed to have linear elastic and orthotropic constitutive laws. The mode is looked for in the form :

$$u(x_1, x_2) = U(x_2) e^{ikx_1}$$

$$v(x_1, x_2) = V(x_2) e^{ikx_1}$$

where k is the wavenumber, $U(x_2)$ the amplitude in the x_1 direction, and $V(x_2)$ the amplitude in the x_2 direction. Writing the bifurcation criterion $\delta^2 P = 0$ leads to a classical eigenvalue problem. Each layer is then discretized in its thickness. Lagrange elements with three nodes are used. The nodal unknowns are the $U(x_2)$ and $V(x_2)$ amplitudes at each node. For each value of the wavenumber, we compute the first eigenvalue. The minimum of the neutral stability curve corresponds to the critical load and the critical wavenumber, when microbuckling occurs.

A series of calculations were performed on fibre-matrix laminates with different values of the thickness. The displacement is assumed to be zero on the lower face, and the upper face is free. Figures 4 and 5 show the numerical results for the critical wavelength and the critical strain versus the

thickness of the composite, in comparison with the homogenized model. A good agreement between the two models is observed. Furthermore, the influence of the loading (flexion or compression) on the instability is clearly shown.

Figure 4. Comparison between the numerical results on the complete microstructure and the homogenized model (critical wavelength)

Figure 5. Comparison between the numerical results on the complete microstructure and the homogenized model (critical strain)

4. CONCLUDING DISCUSSION

Microbuckling is definitely the main phenomenon to explain the strength in compression, because it is a structural instability, depending on the loading and on the stacking sequence. The proposed homogenized model permits to explain qualitatively the influence of the structure on the microbuckling critical strain, and then on the compressive strength. However, the strain level which is obtained with our models is still very high, but in a little while we will be able to propose a similar model including the effects of an initial misalignment of fibres and a non-linearity of the matrix.

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